

MEANING OF COMPOSITION IN PAINTING

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Abstract: This article provides information about the color of fine art and the meaning of composition in painting, its basis in colors and some concepts of composition.

Keywords: Composition, painting, color perspective, perspective, genre, warm tones, cold tones, plot.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены сведения о цвете изобразительного искусства и значении композиции в живописи, ее основе в цветах и некоторых понятиях о композиции.

Ключевые слова: Композиция, картина, цветовая перспектива, перспектива, жанр, теплые тона, холодные тона, сюжет.

The place of culture, education, art and spirituality of our people is incomparable in the future of turning our republic into a great country and joining the ranks of the developed countries of the world. Fine arts play an important role in enriching the spirituality and culture of our people.

Painting is considered one of the types of fine art in which color occupies an important place.

Paintings include works of art painted on a hard flat surface.

A painting means a vivid depiction of life, that is, a complete and convincing depiction of existence.

According to its practical features, painting is divided into monumental, easel, miniature, theatrical and decorative, decorative and other types.

Each of them differs depending on its characteristics, in terms of technique and artistic image. The artistic image of the painting is demonstrative and clear. Artists create works using visual and plastic tools (pencil drawing and composition), and the main means of expression is color.

"Composition" comes from the Latin word and means "composition of the whole", "inseparable connection".

The acceptance of the structure of a work of art based on the content, features and intended purpose is determined in many ways. No sample of fine art, including architecture and folk art, can do without a compositional solution.

In the painting, the composition demonstrates the consistent ideological and plot-thematic basis of the work depicting objects and patterns in the ratio of light and shadow, as well as light spots.

"An artist cannot create a composition without learning to observe, without identifying interesting and important sides for him. It is only after these moments that the artist opens up the possibilities of expressing being, which he considers primary, and when he

begins to understand what the idea is, only formation remains, and the composition is given to him by itself. ..." (Kramskoy).

The composition fully demonstrates its quality and function in thematic paintings. In this case, the main meaning of the composition is to reveal the ideological side of the work of art. In the work of fiction, the action of the plot is considered down to the smallest elements with the help of "director's" means and techniques. Along the way, the artist identifies or defines the personality traits of the participants, expresses their attitude to each other and to the people around them. In this case, the main compositional tools are a group of invented shapes and objects, a clearly found style and impressive facial states and movements, as well as sign language. "Director's" works are performed according to the general spatial and distance structure defined by the artist. The artist's ability to choose perspective, horizon levels, space and the main spatial project is important.

The material and content elements of the composition are constantly moving along with the "special" compositional means that are in constant contact with them. Image Selection:

- Precisely calculated accents and lighting options;
- The ability to use various methods of resistance;
- The correct formation of the rhythmic style of the form depends on this.

Sometimes, in realistic art, composition occupies an independent place, just as we use speech to express our thoughts. The composition is designed to bring the viewer to an understanding of what the artist should express. Realistic composition is not a medium or style and does not attract the viewer. The requirements of strict laws do not interfere with him in each individual case, the artist achieves inner freedom without being tied to any principles.

In each sketch, the artist can achieve the necessary solution to the picture only by giving the necessary movement in the case of a human figure, and in the case of a still life or landscape genre - by giving a certain shape and position.

The artist defines the general plan that is important for the future of the work and what he should focus on.

The elements in the work are not placed randomly, they must correspond to the artist's idea and emphasize the idea of the composition.

One of the first signs of the perfection of a composition is that it can be understood from a distance. If the picture looks fuzzy at a great distance or "dazzles" the eye with its brilliance, then the main professional moment has been missed. Decorating is the basis of compositional skill.

There are a lot of topics for writing, they are not bad, but they can be a bad decision. The future artist will have to choose a theme and achieve an interesting solution to it. To do this, he should carefully observe the surrounding environment. Of course, with a pencil in hand. The student is required to never lose his album, so it is very important that he always keep a brief record of the image and mark interesting and original scenes. All this can be a useful tool when creating a work in the future.

When developing a composition, the moment of the artist's conscious approach may be important, understanding all the criteria, the artist will definitely achieve some kind of result. His experience gained during his work is also of particular importance. It is also important to

turn to classical treasures and follow their laws, pay attention to the advice of the master, who is an example for the artist.

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